

A New Complex of Bivalent Nickel with 2, 2'-Azobisisobutyramidine

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Both cobalt and nickel were observed to form coordination complex with 2, 2'-azobisisobutyramidine in the bivalent state of the metals in neutral or slightly basic medium. Studies on the nickel complex is being reported here. The results of jobs method of continuous variation of concentration and the slope ratio method of Harvey and Manning corresponded to the complex composition as equimolecular. The elemental analysis of the complex also supported this. It has a high extinction at the absorption maxima of $415\text{ m}\mu$ and its dissociation constant in methanol was also determined. From the spectral and other experimental data it seemed that a four coordinated complex involving both the azo and amidine functions were formed. The reaction may be used for quantitative determination of either of the components spectrophotometrically in presence of an excess of the other in neutral or slightly basic medium.

AZOBISISOBUTYRAMIDINES(ABA) form a class of water soluble aro compounds capable of initiating polymerization process and other free radical initiators. It has been observed in this laboratory that they form coordination complexes with bivalent nickel and cobalt in neutral or weakly basic medium. This offers an opportunity of estimating very small amounts of either the metal or the amidine itself. The present communication reports the results on the study of the nickel-ABA complex.

Experiments and Results

Materials : 2, 2' Azobis-isobutyramidine (kindly supplied by Dr. J. Dougherty of Dow Chemical Co.) was prepared from its dihydrochloride salt according to the method of Hammond et al.⁴ The resulting free base was twice recrystallized from dry methanol and finally dried under vacuum.

2, 2' Azobis-isobutyronitrile (Koch light and Co.) was recrystallized from ethanol twice and dried under vacuum.

Acetamidine hydrochloride (Koch Light and Co.) and nickel sulfate (G. R. Quality) were used without any further purification. The concentration of nickel

in methanol solution was estimated gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime method.⁵

Methanol (E. Merck and B.D.H.) was dried over lime and fractionally distilled before use, the middle fraction having a boiling point 64.5°C was collected. Ultraviolet and visible spectra was taken with a single beam Zeiss model VSU 2 spectrophotometer. The measurement of the magnetic moment was carried out in a Guy balance.

Preparation of the complex : The complex was formed in methanol on mixing solutions of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the 2, 2'-azobisisobutyramidine (ABA) both in methanolic solution. Similar nature of the spectra and a new absorption maximum at $415\text{ m}\mu$ obtained on mixing the nickel sulfate and ABA in different proportions indicated the formation of only one type of complex at least under the present experimental conditions. The complex could be isolated from a solution containing a small excess of ABA by precipitating with an excess of acetone. The precipitated complex was recrystallized from dry methanolic solution by keeping in a freezer for several days when dark red needle shaped crystals separated out.

Characteristics of the complex : To apply Job's method¹ of continuous variation, varying amounts

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Fig. 1. Spectra of NiSO_4 , ABA and Ni-ABA

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variation of the reactants.

of nickel sulfate solution in methanol was taken and to it the required quantity of the ABA solution ($1 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) also in methanol was added, so that the final concentration of both the species together remained constant. Fig. 2 represents a typical set of experiments.

The slope ratio method of Harvey and Manning³ was adopted to characterise the nature of the complex. Two sets of solution one containing an excess of NiSO_4 and the other containing an excess of ABA were prepared and their optical densities at 420, 430 and 500 $\text{m}\mu$ were measured. The results are shown in Fig. 3 at the three wave lengths. In all the cases it was observed that the complex was formed by reacting one mole of NiSO_4 with one mole of ABA.

The isolated complex showed identical spectrum as obtained from mixing the two component in solution. The elemental analysis of the complex confirmed the molecular ratio of the components as unity and corresponded to a formula of Ni(ABA)SO_4 .

Fig. 3. Slope-ratio method of Harvey and Manning for the complex.

The absorption maxima of the solutions either made from the isolated complex or from mixing the two components was at 415 mμ. The extinction coefficient was found to be 630 lit mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 415 mμ.

The dissociation constant of the complex in methanol was found out spectrophotometrically using the following principle³. The reaction can be represented as follows assuming M as the metal and A the ligand.

$$\text{The dissociation constant } K = \frac{[M] \times [A]}{[MA]}$$

Now in the presence of a large excess of any of the component M or A the reaction may be assumed to be complete in the right direction. The absorbance due to the complex MA was much more higher than either of the components M and A at the absorption maximum of 415 mμ. So the absorbance of a solution containing a large excess (here 9 times) of one of the components, correcting for the little absorbance due to components may be taken as the measure of the undissociated complex MA. The correct absorbance of a solution containing Ni⁺⁺ and ABA in 1:9 ratio was found to be identical with that of the solution containing the components in just the reverse ratio. Using this value the concentration of undissociated MA in a mixture of 1:1 molar NiSO₄ and ABA

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ALKALI ON THE Ni-ABA COMPLEX IN WATER

Vo. of ABA 2 HCl	Vol. of Ni ⁺⁺	Vol. of KOH solution	Water in ml.	Optical density 420 mμ
3.35 × 10 ⁻⁴ (M)	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴ (M)	6.056 × 10 ⁻² (M)		
2	0.2	0.1	2.7	0.03
2	0.4	0.1	2.5	0.06
2	0.8	0.1	2.1	0.125
2	1.0	0.1	1.9	0.150
1.151 × 10 ⁻³ (M)	3.5 × 10 ⁻⁴ (M)	6.056 × 10 ⁻² (M)		
3	1	0.1	0.9	0.21
3	1	0.2	0.8	0.21
3	1	0.3	0.7	0.205
3	1	0.4	0.6	0.202
3	1	0.5	0.5	0.185
3	1	0.8	0.3	0.180
3	1	1.0	0	0.185

could be determined from the absorbance of the mixture and thus the value of the dissociation constant K was determined. The observed value was 1.157×10^{-8} .

The complex was not very stable in water as is also evident from the standard observed value of the dissociation constant and was found to hydrolyse slowly on keeping the water solution for a long time with the precipitation of nickel. So, though more stable dihydrochloride of the azoamidine (ABA-2HCl) could be used in water solution to produce the complex with Ni^{++} on the addition of alkali, the final solution could not be kept for a long time. Table I shows that in neutral or very slightly alkaline solution the concentration of the complex increased linearly with the increase of Ni^{++} in presence of excess of ABA-2HCl, whereas the extent of complex formation decreased with the increase of alkali concentration in Ni^{++} and ABA 2HCl remaining constant.

Discussion

The reaction followed the Beers law excellently and this can be used as the means for quantitative determination of either of the components colorimetrically provided a neutral or very slightly alkaline medium could be used. The high extinction at the absorption maxima in the visible range of spectrum it is possible to detect very low concentration of Ni in neutral solution.

Azonitriles as well as acetamidine was observed not to form any complex with Ni^{2+} at least under the

experimental condition followed, so it is likely that both the azo and amidine groups were involved in the complex formation. Possibly due to this reason the ultra-violet absorption peak of the azo group disappeared in the complex. From the spectrum of the complex the Ni^{++} can be treated to form a four coordinated complex with each molecule of the ligand. The observed value of the magnetic moment around 1.73, BM of course requires further studies to elucidate the molecular structure of the complex. Disappearance of the absorption at 3400 cm^{-1} due to -N-H stretching frequency by converging with the absorption band of lower frequency due to methyl group to form a plateau in the complex confirmed the involvement of amine group in the complex formation. -C=N stretching frequency at $1650\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was more or less maintained but the absorption of 1170 cm^{-1} lowered and merged with the absorption band at $1150\text{--}1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ possibly due to ionic sulphate.

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